
PLANNING FOR THE FACTORS STIMULATE PRODUCTION: STUDY A STATISTICAL

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ABSTRACT

Communities and nations since ancient times tried to raise , as the main instrument and catalyst for individuals associated with these communities and thus affect the development and boosting prosperity and welfare of the individual and the impact on the public life of the study aimed at identify the most Important variables which directly affect the value of production in the community under study Company for electrical industries to indicate overlap and their association with each other to reach the highest value of production together with the effects of other variables.

Keywords: Statistical Planning, Multicollinearity, Stimulate Production, Correlations.

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INTRODUCTION

The industrial policy in Iraq faces today a mission and objectives to change the local manufacturing compass, where the objectives and tasks are focused on the implementation of a national industrial policy that achieves real industrial growth that contributes to the national economy by its success and diversification through the adoption and encouragement of large domestic industries The revenues of the oil revenues to encourage the small and medium industries run by the public sector and private and try to enter the local and regional market and diversify the country's imports of hard currency, and this transformation as a result of developments in local and international conditions. At the domestic level, it is the beginning of the implementation of the economic reform program, the transition to a diversified market economy and the liberalization of economic activities, foremost of which are industrial activities. At the international level, the pace of technological progress and economic globalization is accompanied by the dismantling of large industries to a number of small production units and their distribution to different countries according to comparative advantage and productive efficiency.

Thus considerations of production efficiency, quality and export competitiveness affect other considerations. The process of the exchange of industrial goods in the international markets[1].

Iraq has made strides in the process of economic development. It is now facing new opportunities and challenges that require it to change its economic and industrial path in order to cope with the developments in the economy. Aware of the importance of developing a strategy for industrial development in Iraq, this study was prepared as a first step in the study of the most important factors entering and stimulating the production through an applied study of the electrical and electronic industries in Iraq.

RESEARCH AIMS

Research objective: The research aims to study some variables that affect the value of production and increase its quantities to determine the extent of correlation and overlap among them through the use of appropriate statistical methods.

The importance of research

The study of increasing the production of important economic studies, which researchers have been diligent in knowing the impact of the factors involved and interrelated in the economic process and the impact on the profitability function of the plant or laboratory and to identify the most critical points and try to address

Limits of research

The limits of the temporal search were extended between 3. December, 2015 and 8. February, 2016. At the company's site in Baghdad-alwaziriyah , the data was collected based on data obtained through personal interviews, interviews with officials and the adoption of official reports.

Method of research

Using the statistical method called linearity problem to analyze the most important variables affecting the adopted variable Y (value of production) through the factors involved in the society in question.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. linear multi (duplex linear) Multicolinearity Problem: the problem of linear multi appears when two or more of the explanatory variables associated with a linear relationship so that it becomes difficult to separate the impact of each and every one of them, adopted to that variable Add[2]. Linear phenomenon of double taxation may occur when the value of one explanatory variables equal to all views, as it means that the column represents a variable in the matrix is equal to the first column of which multiplied by a constant note that this problem may show whether the appreciation of the features of the model is subject to the hypothesis of homogeneity or heterogeneity, and both took data variables illustrations we Approved the form of time or CT chains variable, but often face this problem, namely[3], the linear interference problem when using the time series data as economic variables are affected usually the same factors over time and thus change the same pattern, which generates a link in writing among them[4].

2. The hypothesis of linear multiplicity can therefore be summarized as follows
3. There is no complete or almost complete linear relationship between any of the explanatory variables. The number of parameters to be estimated must be less than the sample size. That is, the number of columns of the matrix X which is amounted (K+1) must be less than the number of rows (n), which is in other words[5]:

$$r(X) = K + 1 < n \dots\dots 1$$

$r(x)$ represents the rank of the matrix X^5

Where it is not possible to find a uniform estimate of the parameters of the linear model. when there is a complete linear relationship between two or more explanatory variables. This is because the inverse matrix of information ($X'X$) does not exist where the parameter of this matrix in this case is equal to zero[6].

2. Testing the existence of linear multiplicity between the variables in the study[7]: Most of the tests for double-linearity depend on the correlation coefficients between the explanatory variables in the linear model studied. The most important of these tests is known as the Farrar-Glauber test. This test is based on the Kay square statistic (X^2) and according to the following formula[8]:

$$X^2 = - \left[n - 1 - \frac{1}{6}(2K + 5) \right] - \text{Ln}|D| \dots\dots 2$$

Where n represents the sample size and K represents the number of independent variables and $\text{Ln}|D|$ represents the natural logarithm of a matrix parameter for the following correlation coefficients

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & r_{12} & r_{13} & \dots & r_{1k} \\ r_{21} & 1 & r_{23} & \dots & r_{2k} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & 1 & \dots & r_{3k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{k1} & r_{k2} & r_{k3} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} :$$

Then we put the following null hypothesis $H_0: X_j$. versus alternative hypothesis $r_s H_1: X_j$ and compares the process value calculated X^2 under the previous formula with the theoretical value X^2 (Tabulated) thermal degree equal to $\left(\frac{K(K-1)}{-2}\right)$ the level of a certain significance . If the process value is greater than the tabular value we reject the hypothesis H_0 and accept the hypothesis H_1 that there is a multiple overlap between the independent variables and vice versa[9].

We should be here to mention that the linear diversity problem that emerged here in our research dealt with trying to expand the sample size and thus the possibility of obtaining sufficient data on the phenomenon variables under research and generally is treated in the case of multi-linear completely delete the illustration variable or explanatory variables that are closely in writing fully With the rest of the independent variables in the model. Therefore[10], the method of treatment varies depending on the severity of the linear diversity among them the style of time-series data and CT and the use of the least squares method restricted (Restricted least square) or the style of the (Ridge Regression), and finally the way the main vehicles (Principal Components) [11].

3. The applied side

The data were obtained by direct interview and the previous reports and to interview the officials and workers on the production lines in the electrical and electronic industries company located on the website <http://www.sceei.gov.iq/> where they were arranged and classified and then each variable was defined As follows:

Y = Different production quantities (by quality) of the stock company.

X₁=The equity capital used by the product line type

X₂=Number of workers (labor force)

X₃=Time (working hours)

C. If the calculated value falls between the two values $d_L < d^* < d_u$, it means that there is no certainty of self-correlation and so on.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Definition of the society under study (Electrical Industries Company):

The General Company for Electrical Industries is one of the companies of the Ministry of Industry and Minerals, which has been greatly supported by the State as well as all the activities of the industrial sector in order to promote them to play an important role in achieving the development goals, especially that the development of this sector reflects the level of economic growth of the country and has taken the production of engines, To develop their products both qualitatively and qualitatively to meet the local market needs of these products.

Company Objective: The company aims to provide its products to all citizens with good quality and reasonable prices for its importance in the public life of all citizens, relying on the methods of modern development and the most use of the production process and to identify the value and quantity of production with the study of the variables involved and interrelated and affecting the process of production and specifications Iraqi standard to reach the highest level of production.

Activities of company:

- 1 - The above company undertakes various activities for the public interest in the government departments and all citizens by selling directly from its exhibitions located in the regions of Baghdad-Waziriya- and in partnership with the electronic industries in Abu Nwas and at suitable prices.
- 2 - Participate in various exhibitions inside and outside Iraq and to display their products and to promote them has been well received by the buyers.
- 3- The company plays a role in the national economy through funds transferred to the state treasury.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data was processed by testing whether there was a linear interference between the explanatory variables collected by the researcher and as shown in the statistical analysis which are distributed on 6 lines:

- 1-Transformers.
- 2-Generators.
- 3-Fans.
- 4-Heaters.
- 5-Water pumps.
- 6-electricspare parts Other lines under implementation not mentioned

							Sum
Y	15	13	40	16	24	12	120
X1	580	640	630	690	1400	860	4800
X2	16	20	26	17	19	16	114
X3	6	8	9	6	7	6	42
$X_1 - \bar{X}_1$	-220	-160	-170	-110	600	60	0
$X_2 - \bar{X}_2$	-3	0	-2	7	1	-3	0
$X_3 - \bar{X}_3$	-1	1	2	-1	0	-1	0
X_1^2	48400	25600	28900	12100	36000	3600	478600
X_2^2	9	1	49	4	0	9	72
X_3^2	1	1	4	1	0	1	8
X_1X_2	660	-160	-1190	220	0	-180	-650
X_1X_3	220	-160	-340	110	0	-60	-230
X_2X_3	3	1	14	2	0	3	23

$$\bar{Y} = 20, \quad \bar{X}_1 = 800, \quad \bar{X}_2 = 19, \quad \bar{X}_3 = 7$$

H0: There is no multi-line correlation.

H1: There is a multiple linear correlation.

$$X_c^2 = \left(\frac{K}{3} - n + \frac{3}{2}\right) \text{Ln}D \dots 3$$

$$r_{12} = \frac{\sum X_1X_2}{\sqrt{\sum X_1^2 \sum X_2^2}} = \frac{-650}{\sqrt{478600(72)}} = \frac{-650}{5870.195} = -0.11$$

$$r_{13} = \frac{\sum X_1X_3}{\sqrt{\sum X_1^2 \sum X_3^2}} = \frac{-230}{\sqrt{478600(8)}} = \frac{-230}{1956.731} = -0.117$$

$$r_{23} = \frac{\sum X_2X_3}{\sqrt{\sum X_2^2 \sum X_3^2}} = \frac{23}{\sqrt{(72)(8)}} = \frac{23}{576} = 0.958$$

$$\therefore D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -0.11 & -0.117 \\ -0.11 & 1 & 0.958 \\ -0.117 & 0.958 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0.0811$$

$$X_c^2 = \left(\frac{4}{3} - 6 + \frac{2}{3}\right) \text{Ln}(0.0811) = 7.954$$

$$X_{(0.05,3)}^2 = 7.814$$

$$\therefore X_c^2 > X_{(0.05,3)}^2$$

If we reject H₀ and accept H₁ this means there is linear interference.

Then we use the F test to get

$$R^2_{X_1 \cdot X_2 \cdot X_3} = \frac{R^2_{X_1X_2} + R^2_{X_1X_3} - 2R_{X_1X_2} \cdot R_{X_1X_3} \cdot R_{X_2X_3}}{1 - R^2_{X_2X_3}} \dots 4$$

$$= \frac{0.0121 + 0.013689 - 2(-0.11)(-0.117)(0.958)}{1 - 0.917764} = 0.0137$$

$$F_1 = \frac{R^2_{X_1.X_2X_3}/(K-2)}{(1-R^2_{X_1.X_2X_3})/(n-K+1)} = \frac{0.01374/2}{0.9862/3} = 0.02$$

$$H_0: R^2_{X_1.X_2X_3} = 0$$

$$H_1: R^2_{X_1.X_2X_3} \neq 0$$

$$F_{t(2,3,0.01)} = 30.817$$

$$\therefore F_1 < F_{(0.01,2,3)}$$

If we accept H_0 that means that there is no correlations - between X_1 and other variables [7]

$$R^2_{X_2.X_1X_3} = \frac{R^2_{X_2X_1} + R^2_{X_2X_3} - 2R_{X_2X_1} \cdot R_{X_2X_3} \cdot R_{X_1X_3}}{1 - R^2_{X_1X_3}} \dots 5$$

$$= \frac{0.0121 + 0.9177 - 2(-0.11)(0.958)(-0.117)}{1 - 0.013689}$$

$$= 0.9177$$

$$F_2 = \frac{R^2_{X_2.X_1X_3}/(K-2)}{(1-R^2_{X_2.X_1X_3})/(n-K+1)} = \frac{(0.9177/2)}{(0.0823/3)} = 16.726$$

$$H_0: R^2_{X_2.X_1X_3} = 0$$

$$H_1: R^2_{X_2.X_1X_3} \neq 0$$

$$F_{t(2,3,0.01)} = 30.817$$

$$\therefore F_2 < F_{(0.01,2,3)}$$

If we accept H_0 that means there is no correlations between X_2 and other variables..

$$R^2_{X_3.X_1X_2} = \frac{R^2_{X_3X_1} + R^2_{X_3X_2} - 2R_{X_3X_1} \cdot R_{X_3X_2} \cdot R_{X_1X_2}}{1 - R^2_{X_1X_2}} \dots 6$$

$$= \frac{0.013689 + 0.917764 - 2(-0.117)(0.958)(-0.11)}{1 - 0.0121}$$

$$= 0.91790$$

$$F_3 = \frac{R^2_{X_3.X_1X_2}/(K-2)}{(1-R^2_{X_3.X_1X_2})/(n-K+1)} = \frac{(0.91790/2)}{(0.0821/3)} = 16.770$$

$$H_0: R^2_{X_3.X_1X_2} = 0$$

$$H_1: R^2_{X_3.X_1X_2} \neq 0$$

$$F_{t(2,3,0.01)} = 30.8$$

$$\therefore F_3 < F_{(0.01,2,3)}$$

If we accept H_0 that means there is no correlation between X_3 and other variables

Then we use T test to get - :

$$r_{X_1X_2.X_3} = \frac{r_{X_1X_2} - r_{X_1X_3} r_{X_2X_3}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2_{X_1X_3})(1-r^2_{X_2X_3})}} \dots 7$$

$$= \frac{(-0.11) - (-0.117)(0.958)}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.013689)(1 - 0.917764)}} = \frac{0.002086}{0.2847} = 0.00732$$

$$T_{X_1X_2} = \frac{(0.00732)\sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.0005358)}} = 0.0126$$

$H_0: r_{X_1X_2, X_3} = 0$
 $H_1: r_{X_1X_2, X_3} \neq 0$
 $T_{(0.01, 3)} = 5.541$
 $\therefore T_{X_1, X_2} < T_t$

If we reject H_0 and accept H_1 that means there is no correlations between X_2 and X_3 .

$$r_{X_1X_3, X_2} = \frac{r_{X_1X_3} - r_{X_1X_2}r_{X_3X_2}}{\sqrt{(1 - r^2_{X_1X_2})(1 - r^2_{X_3X_2})}} \dots 8$$

$$= \frac{(-0.117) - (-0.11)(0.958)}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.0121)(1 - 0.9177)}} = -0.04$$

$$T_{X_1X_3} = \frac{(0.00732)\sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.0005358)}} = 0.0126$$

$H_0: r_{X_1X_3, X_2} = 0$
 $H_1: r_{X_1X_3, X_2} \neq 0$
 $T_t = 4.541$
 $\therefore T_{X_1, X_3} < T_t$

If we accept H_0 that means there is no correlations between X_1 and other variables..

$$r_{X_2X_3, X_1} = \frac{r_{X_2X_3} - r_{X_2X_1}r_{X_3X_1}}{\sqrt{(1 - r^2_{X_2X_1})(1 - r^2_{X_3X_1})}} \dots 9$$

$$= \frac{(0.958) - (-0.11)(-0.117)}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.0121)(1 - 0.013689)}} = 0.9574$$

$$T_{X_2X_3} = \frac{(0.9574)\sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{(1 - 0.9166146)}} = 5.742$$

$H_0: r_{X_2X_3, X_1} = 0$
 $H_1: r_{X_2X_3, X_1} \neq 0$
 $T_t = 4.541$
 $\therefore T_{X_2, X_3} > T_t$

If we reject H_0 and accept H_1 that means there is no correlations between X_2 and X_3 .

CONCLUSION

1- Adopting the appropriate statistical treatments to study the dimensions of the problem in question to find out the errors contained in the production quantities.

2-The use of modern computer applications and appropriate programs, namely the use of information technology in the control of different stages of production.

3-Most inspection and workers inspectors lack experience in the field of production control in addition to inaccuracy in recording *data*.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1-We recommend that researchers in this field should be a statistical study of similar problems of study similar to increase the size of the sample and the use of advanced methods in the calculation of multiple linear interference, such as the method of data reduction (Redceing variables) or Restricted least squares.

2-In our research, we found that there was an overlap between X2 and X3 with the exclusion of X1 and that the best method of processing was to increase the size of the sample.

3-Data collection, classification and classification should be collected according to the type of study and the statistical methods prepared in advance using the previous experiences of researchers in this field. The researcher should rely on himself to collect the data in order to avoid the mistakes of the employees responsible for recording the data to reach credibility in the results.

4- Use of statistical programs such as SPSS program and benefit from it.

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